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Effect of dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) intake on testicular atrophy induced by di(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate (DEHP)

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Abstract

Objective: To clarify the inhibitory effect of dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO), known as a free radical scavenger, on di(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate (DEHP)-induced testicular atrophy, oral administration experiments were conducted using rats.

Methods: Four-week-old male SD rats were divided into control, DEHP, and DEHP/DMSO groups (6 rats per group). The treatment groups were fed 1% (w/w) DEHP diets and 1% (w/w) DMSO water for two weeks.

Results: Obvious testicular atrophy was observed in the DEHP group. On the other hand, the testis weight of the DEHP/DMSO group was slightly higher than that of the DEHP alone group. The relationship between relative testicular weight and plasma MEHP (a DEHP metabolite) concentration or testicular tissue MEHP concentration showed a significant negative correlation in both the DEHP alone group and the DEHP/DMSO group, suggesting that the decrease in testicular weight is dependent on MEHP concentration. Furthermore, the slope of the regression line in the DEHP/DMSO group was gentler than that of the DEHP alone group, suggesting that DMSO administration has an inhibitory effect on the decrease in testicular weight. On the other hand, in the relationship between plasma MEHP concentration and testicular MEHP concentration, DMSO administration tended to increase the distribution of MEHP to testicular tissue, suggesting that it may reduce the effect of DMSO in suppressing testicular atrophy.

Conclusion: DMSO, known as a free radical scavenger, has been found to slightly inhibit testicular atrophy caused by DEHP. However, DMSO may increase the distribution of the active toxic substance MEHP to the testes, and therefore may reduce the effect of DMSO in suppressing testicular atrophy.

Keywords: Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO), DEHP, MEHP, testicular atrophy.

Introduction

Polyvinyl chloride products containing di(2-ethylhexyl)phthalate (DEHP) are used in a very wide range of applications, including building materials, household goods, toys, and medical devices, so exposure to DEHP is common in daily life. Animal studies have shown that DEHP can cause testicular atrophy [1-5], and there are concerns that environmental exposure may have adverse effects on humans [6, 7]. The mechanism of toxicity is not fully understood, but it is thought to be closely related to phthalate metabolites such as mono(2-ethylhexyl)phthalate (MEHP) stimulating peroxisome proliferator-activated receptors [8-10] and generating oxidative stress [11]. MEHP induces oxidative stress in germ cells and causes apoptosis of spermatocytes as the direct action of MEHP on germ cells [12, 13].

On the other hand, dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO), a hydroxyl radical scavenger, is known to have potent antioxidant and apoptosis inhibitory effects [14-16]. Furthermore, DMSO is known to have radioprotective and anti-inflammatory effects [17-19], and its application in the pharmaceutical field is being studied. Therefore, improvement of testicular atrophy by suppressing oxidative stress is expected. The authors report on the effects of concurrent consumption of drinking water containing DMSO on toxicity in rats exposed to dietary DEHP.

Materials and Methods

Chemicals and animal diet

DEHP and DMSO with a chemical purity of 97% or higher were purchased from Wako Pure Chemical Industries, Ltd. (Osaka). The CE-2 diets (Clea, Tokyo, Japan) containing DEHP was prepared by Oriental Yeast Company (Chiba, Japan). MEHP was purchased from Tokyo Kasei Kogyo Co.,Ltd. (Tokyo, Japan). All other chemicals were of the highest grade available from commercial sources.

Animals and ethics

Male Sprague-Dawley rats aged three-week-old purchased from Charles River (Kanagawa, Japan) were housed at the Laboratory Animal Center of Kagawa University. They were acclimated at 22–24 °C and 50–60% relative humidity with a 12-h light/dark cycle. The experiment protocols had the approval by the Kagawa University Animal Committee.

Experimental design

Four-week-old rats weighing 94–104 g were divided into three groups: a control group, a DEHP group, and a DEHP/DMSO group, with six rats in each group. The DEHP group was given a diet containing 1% (w/w) DEHP and tap water, while the DEHP/DMSO group was given a diet containing 1% (w/w) DEHP and water containing 1% (w/w) DMSO for two weeks. The control group was given normal diet and tap water. After the experiment, the rats were sacrificed under ether anesthesia. The testes were removed and weighed. Plasma and testes were frozen and stored at -40°C until MEHP measurement.

MEHP analysis in plasma and testis

The MEHP levels in organs and plasma were determined by high performance liquid chromatography [20].

Statistical analysis

Results were expressed as means \pm standard deviations (SD). A one-way ANOVA test followed by Tukey's multiple comparison test was performed to compare treatment groups. A value of $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

Results

Table 1 shows body weight and testicular weight. In the DEHP-treated group, body weight was slightly lower than in the control group, but the difference was statistically significant, and testicular weight was also significantly lower than in the control group. In the DEHP/DMSO group, body weight was almost the same as in the control group, but testicular weight or relative testicular weight (as a percentage of body weight) was slightly higher than in the DEHP group.

As shown in Table 2, MEHP concentrations in plasma and testis in the DEHP/DMSO group were slightly higher than in the DEHP group. As shown in Figure 1, the relative testicular weights of the control and DEHP groups showed a strong negative correlation with plasma MEHP concentration and testicular MEHP concentration, and a strong positive correlation was shown between plasma MEHP concentration and testicular MEHP concentration. In contrast, the relative testicular weights of the control and DEHP/DMSO groups showed significant negative correlations with plasma MEHP concentration and testicular MEHP concentration, and the slope of the regression line was more moderate than that of the control and DEHP groups. In addition, the relationship between plasma MEHP concentration and testicular MEHP concentration shows a tendency for DMSO treatment to increase the distribution ratio of MEHP between plasma and testicular tissue.

Table 1. Body weight and testicular weight of DEHP and DMSO-administered rats. Relative testicular weight; testes/body (%). * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$, as compared to control, # $p < 0.05$, ## $p < 0.01$, ### $p < 0.001$, as compared to DEHP.

	Control (n=6)		DEHP (n=6)		DEHP/DMSO (n=6)	
	mean	SD	mean	SD	mean	SD
Initial body weight (g)	98.7	2.1	97.7	3.1	99.3	1.5
Final body weight (g)	217.8	8.3#	201.8	9.7*	209.0	10.8
Testes (g)	2.06	0.21###	0.99	0.26***	1.14	0.29***
Relative testicular weight (%)	0.95	0.09###	0.49	0.13***	0.55	0.15***

Table 2. Plasma and testicular MEHP concentrations. BDL: below the detection limit.

	Control (n=6)		DEHP (n=6)		DEHP/DMSO (n=6)	
	mean	SD	mean	SD	mean	SD
Plasma MEHP ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	BDL		40.3	13.0	51.9	10.2
Testicular MEHP ($\mu\text{g/g}$)	BDL		3.3	0.8	6.4	3.5

Figure 1. Relationship between relative testicular weight, plasma MEHP and testicular MEHP

Discussion

Oral exposure to high concentrations of DEHP causes testicular atrophy in rodents [1-8]. MEHP, the active metabolite of DEHP, stimulates peroxisome proliferator-activated receptors and increases carbohydrate and lipid metabolism [21-23]. The oxidative stress generated may be closely related to DEHP toxicity. In the present study, the author examined the effect of DMSO, a potent radical scavenger, on DEHP-induced testicular atrophy.

Obvious testicular atrophy was observed in the DEHP alone group. On the other hand, the testis weight of the DEHP/DMSO group was slightly higher than that of the DEHP alone group. The relationship between relative testicular weight and plasma MEHP (DEHP metabolite) concentration or testicular tissue MEHP concentration showed a significant negative correlation in both the DEHP alone group and the DEHP/DMSO group, suggesting that the decrease in testicular weight is dependent on MEHP concentration. Furthermore, the slope of the regression line in the DEHP/DMSO exposure group was gentler than that of the DEHP-only group, suggesting that DMSO administration has an inhibitory effect on the decrease in testicular weight. On the other hand, in the relationship between plasma MEHP concentration and testicular MEHP concentration, DMSO administration tended to increase the distribution of MEHP to testicular tissue, suggesting that it may reduce the effect of DMSO in suppressing testicular atrophy.

Conclusion

DMSO, known as a free radical scavenger, has been found to slightly inhibit testicular atrophy caused by DEHP. However, DMSO may increase the distribution of the active toxic substance MEHP to the testes, and therefore may reduce the effect of DMSO in suppressing testicular atrophy.

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

There is no conflict of interest in this work.

Statement of ethical approval

The experiment protocols had the approval by the Kagawa University Animal Committee.

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